

Actual vs Predicted (UVVariance)

Standardized Residuals (UVVariance)

Partial Regression Plot (UVVariance)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.4244$$

Interpretation:

1 = positive autocorrelation

2 = no autocorrelation

4 = negative autocorrelation

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 11.0707

p-value: 0.0009

Conclusion: Heteroskedasticity Exists

White Test

White Statistic: 11.3178

df: 2

p-value: 0.0035

Conclusion: Heteroskedasticity Exists

Histogram of Residuals (UVVariance)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – UVVariance

